

Paper Chromatography in the Separation of Ions. Effect of Thiocyanate

A. K. Majumdar and M. K. Das

The effect of thiocyanate on the R_f and R_i values of elements of analytical group II to IV has been studied by ascending paper chromatography. The R_f values and the sequences of separation as obtained have been tabulated.

Thiocyanate, an excellent complexing agent, was used in paper chromatography by Arden *et al.*¹, Burstall *et al.*², Martin³, Kertes and Beck⁴ and more recently by Imai⁵.

During the course of paper chromatographic work⁶⁻¹⁰ on the separation of ions, common and rare, in this laboratory various complex formers were used except thiocyanate. This paper reports the effect of thiocyanate on the separation of ions of the analytical groups II to IV by ascending paper chromatography with solvent consisting of acetone, water, hydrochloric or nitric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used and the procedure adopted were the same as described in earlier papers (*loc. cit.*). The test solutions were prepared from chlorides or nitrates of the metals. For vanadate or molybdate and tungstate, ammonium and sodium salts, respectively, were used.

Solvents used are :

- A Acetone, water and hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.18) in the ratio 70:20:10.
- B Solvent A with 1% ammonium thiocyanate.
- C Acetone, water and nitric acid (sp. gr. 1.42) in the ratio 70:20:10.
- D Solvent C with 1% ammonium thiocyanate.

1. Arden, Burstall, Davies, Lewis and Linstead, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 601.
2. Burstall, Davies, Linstead and Wells, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 516.
3. Martin, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1951, 5, 511.
4. Kertes and Beck, *J. Chromatography*, 1959, 2, 362.
5. Imai, *J. Chem. Soc., Japan, Pure Chem. Sect.*, 1961, 82, 1176.
6. Majumdar and Chakrabarty, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 415.
7. Majumdar and Chakrabarty, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 129.
8. Majumdar and Chakrabarty, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 132.
9. Majumdar and Mukherjee, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 19, 480.
10. Majumdar and P. I., *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1960, 174, 429.

TABLE I

R values ± 0.02 Temp. = 36-38°C

Ions	Solvent A		Solvent B		Solvent C		Solvent D	
	R_f	R_r	R_f	R_L	R_f	R_L	R_f	R_L
Hg ²⁺	0.97	1.0	0.98	1.0	0.97	1.0	0	1.0 t
Pb ²⁺	0.68	0.73	0.63	0.70	0.27	0.32	0.25	0.32
Bi ³⁺	0.97	1.0	0.91	0.95	0.85	0.96	0	1.0 t
Cu ²⁺	0.62	0.67	0.97	1.0	0.44	0.49	0	1.0 t
Cd ²⁺	0.98	1.0	0.98	1.0	0.42	0.46	0.55	0.60
As ³⁺	0.65	0.71	0.62	0.68	0.39	0.44	0.39	0.44
Sb ³⁺	0.98	1.0	0.94	0.97	0.74	0.80	0	1.0 t
Sn ²⁺	0.98	1.0	0.96	0.99	0.98	1.0	0.98	1.0
Be ²⁺	0.65	0.74	0.67	0.76	0.67	0.78	0.63	0.71
Al ³⁺	0.28	0.38	0.28	0.36	0.32	0.42	0.28	0.35
Cr ³⁺	0	0.40 t						
Fe ²⁺	0.98	1.0	0.98	1.0	0.32	0.40	0.98	1.0
Th ⁴⁺	0.12	0.16	0.14	0.27	0.85	0.90	0.85	0.95
UO ₂ ²⁺	0.78	0.82	0.47	1.0	0.88	0.94	0.94	1.0
Co ²⁺	0.33	0.39	0.96	1.0	0.26	0.36	0.98	1.0
							0.55	0.75
Ni ²⁺	0.26	0.34	0.31	0.42	0.25	0.35	0.28	0.34
Mn ²⁺	0.34	0.40	0.35	0.41	0.37	0.45	0.34	0.43
Zn ²⁺	0.95	1.0	0.95	1.0	0.34	0.45	0.35	0.49
Ca ²⁺	0.24	0.34	0.26	0.34	0.36	0.42	0.34	0.40
Sr ²⁺	0.13	0.19	0.18	0.22	0.23	0.28	0.24	0.29
Ba ²⁺	0.05	0.10	0.07	0.11	0.13	0.17	0.15	0.18
VO ₂ ⁺	0.40	0.50	0.97	1.0	0.38	0.48	0.98	1.0
WO ₄ ²⁻	0.98	1.0	0.98	1.0	0	0.40 t	0	0.40 t
MoO ₄ ²⁻	0.98	1.0	0.98	1.0	0.12	0.30	0.98	1.0

t = trailing. R_T and R_f have the usual significance.

TABLE II

Solvents	Sequences of separation
A	(Cu, As or Pb) - (Hg, Bi, Cd, Sb or Sn) Th-Al-Be-U-Fe ; Cr-Be-U-Fe (Ni, Co or Mn) - Zn Ba-Sr-Ca VO ₅ ' - (WO ₅ " or MoO ₅ "')
B	(Pb or As) - Bi - (Hg, Cu, Cd, Sb or Sn) [Th-Al] - Be - (U or Fe) ; Cr-Be-(U or Fe) (Ni or Mn) - (Co or Zn) Ba-Sr-Ca
C	Pb - (Cu, Cd or As) - Sb - [Bi-(Hg or Sn)] (Al, Fe or Cr) - Be - (Th or U) Ba-Sr-Ca MoO ₅ " - VO ₅ '.
D	Pb-As-Cd-Sn (Al or Cr) - Be - [Th-(U or Fe)] (Ni, Mn or Zn) - Co Ba-Sr-Ca WO ₅ " - (VO ₅ ' or MoO ₅ "')

Square bracket indicates some portions of the zones are common.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The R_F and R_L values and the sequences of separations are given in Tables I and II. Table I shows the R_F and R_L values of ions after proper development in solvents with or without ammonium thiocyanate. In Table II has been recorded the sequences of separations. Solvents with low acid concentration do not give satisfactory results whereas in higher acid concentration the solvent mixture is not stable. Again, even though a little quantity of thiocyanate is enough to form the complexes, stability of the latter is not maintained unless one percent of the thiocyanate, which is the optimum concentration, is used.

The formation of soluble anionic complexes is generally marked by a less diffused and distinct spot as is found with the ions of Cu, Cd, Fe, U and Mo (see Table I). Comet shape or long bands or formation of more than one spot may be suggested to be due to the partial decomposition of their thiocyanate complexes as has been observed with Hg, Bi, Sb, Cu and Co in solvent D.

The type and nature of the complexes formed by the ions are in conformity with the result obtained in the solvent extraction¹¹ and ion-exchange^{12,13} studies. It can be seen from Table I that the R values of Hg, Bi, Cu, Cd, Sb, Fe, U, Co, V and Mo are much influenced by thiocyanate as expected.

Thus the use of thiocyanate as a complexing agent elucidates the nature of the complexes it forms with the metal ions. When the sequences of separation with solvent A and C are compared with those of B and D, it is evident that a few separations which are not attained otherwise, are achieved easily with thiocyanate.

DEPARTMENT OF INORGANIC AND
ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA 32.

Received, May 16, 1966.

11. Morrison and Froiser, "Solvent Extraction in Analytical Chemistry", New York, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. (1957) p. 135.
12. Turner, Philip and Day. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1962, 26, 94.
13. Majumdar and Mitra, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1965, 208, 1.